

TEACHING LITERATURE IN HOSPITAL EDUCATION THROUGH DIDACTIC GAMES AND NON-TRADITIONAL EDUCATIONAL METHODS

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Annotation: this article talks about teaching literature in hospital education on the basis of didactic game and non-traditional educational methods, to increase patient students' interest in literary science, and through it their passion for life and learning, to expand their worldview, to teach independent thinking.

Keywords: "Meharli maktab", hospital Education, individual lesson, class in the hybrid method, literature science, didactic game, non-traditional educational methods.

The large-scale reforms carried out in the socio-political sphere in our country are aimed at the fate of the Motherland, the prosperity of the people, the education of a new generation, the future governors of an independent country.

It is known that the head of our state Sh.M.Mirziyoyev is looking at the issue of development of the educational and educational system and the field of Science in our country, the development of the growing young generation as the most important direction of state policy. As a practical expression of this, the decision of our government "on measures to introduce a system of preschool education and education and general secondary education for children undergoing treatment at the Center for Pediatric Hematology, Oncology and Clinical Immunology" was adopted.

In accordance with the resolution, the state educational institution "Meharli maktab" based on hospital education was established to effectively organize the processes of preschool education and general secondary education for children being treated in the center of Hematology, Oncology and Clinical Immunology of children.

The institution has the status of a legal entity and was established under the Ministry of preschool and school education. Currently, its branches in the Republic of Karakalpakstan, Andijan and Fergana regions are also operating.

Hospital education is a section of pedagogy related to the organization of education for children who are in long-term treatment and cannot go to educational institutions for health reasons.

In the educational institution "Meharli maktab", classes are organized in a group (class) in a single (individual) order or hybrid way, depending on the general condition of the student.

The organization of a lesson in a single (individual) way is the organization of the lesson – in cases where, according to the doctor's conclusion, the student is not allowed to go to the classroom, the pedagogical employee goes to his room and organizes the lesson.

While the hybrid method of transporting a lesson is to involve students whose age and class are close to each other in the classroom at the same time. In this, it is necessary to comply with medical and hygienic rules (disinfection of all educational equipment, the

presence of a medical mask in all students and teachers, frequent use of an antiseptic, etc.) a lesson process is organized with full validity.

The "**Mehrli maktab**" is a hearth of healing and Science full of affection. Usually the expression of affection is manifested in sincerity, shirinso, in increasing their passion for life and learning by spiritually encouraging readers. In the process, the power and power of the word are unlimited. And the power of the word is difficult to imagine without the science of literature.

Literature is the art of speech. Literature is the most influential tool for the formation of high spirituality in a person. Nameless feelings in a person, subtle experiences, glances of mental state, which can be seen with the eyes, heard with the ear, held by hand and not to taste with the tongue, can only be expressed with the help of words.

The use of didactic game and non-traditional educational methods in the interesting organization of literature lessons of hospital education helps to increase the effectiveness of the educational process, the interest and activity of students in the science of literature. In these lessons, the learning process of students is harmonized with the activities of the game.

Below we will get acquainted with some didactic games and unconventional educational methods that can be used in the literature lessons of hospital education.

Find the hero:

On the table are collected a number of works of art, which were read in Literature lessons. The teacher gives a description to the hero of one of these works. Readers will have to find out which hero is talking about based on these characters and which one is the hero of the work. It is advisable to choose the hero who went through various difficult situations in life, overcoming obstacles and achieving his goal. Because such heroes serve as a powerful motivation for hospital schoolchildren to overcome the disease and achieve their own goals. It can be used in both individual and group classes of hospital education.

Option 1: since he is the right word, honest, brave, resourceful and diligent, no evil force can come to him. (Answer: Gans in the fairy tale "Botir tikuvchi")

Option 2: they overcame all the difficulties and looked for a place where there was a hole in the grass, a hole in the water. (The answer is the heroes of the tale "Susambil")

Option 3: one of them defeats the lion, the second defeats the dragon, the third defeats the thieves. (Answer: Uch og`a-ini botirlar in the fairy tale "the three Oga-ini dives")

The wrong sentence game:

This game is based on pictures. The teacher also uses non-Adib sentences in the process of describing the image of a particular Adib, whose life and work are studied in Literature lessons. Readers should find this sentence with elegance. Students are required to be elegant, meticulous, observant, and attentive during this game. That is, they listen while observing the photo. Being able to find each wrong sentence will gain their meticulousness, self-confidence and interest in the lesson. This game can be used in both individual lesson training and group lessons.

"What is he doing?" ("pantamimo") game:

One of the students goes out to the children and communicates the actions of the hero of any work of art to his peers by showing them through silent actions.

Together, the team of students should comment on his actions. Such a game is played in Literature lessons so that students grow their speech and elegance and do not get bored.

The day and night game:

The teacher writes two or more creative names on the board. Students Command "night" after reading. Children close their eyes. They put themselves to sleep. The teacher replaces any letter or syllables in the words. After the command "day", students open their eyes and determine what changes have taken place. This game can also be used in both shawaks of hospital education

Dream Me game:

This game can be held during the moments of rest that students will have in literature classes in order to concentrate on. The teacher makes the papers with the names of the works of art upside down on the table. One of the readers chooses one of the papers, and looking at this paper should describe the work with its name in it in such a way that the rest of the readers should respond with a quick understanding of which work the sentence is going about. It is advisable to use this game only in group lessons

Option 1: this is a work belonging to the novel genre. It features the life of our grandfather Babur Mirza. (Answer: "Yulduzli tunlar")

Option 2: The author of this story is sharp Hoshimov. It depicts the events of the war period. The work has the images of a sick brother and a monteur brother (answer: "Urushning so'nggi qurboni")

Option 3: the author of this poem is the poet Muhammad Yusuf. In it, the homeland is praised. Throughout the poem, Othman talks about such creators as Nazareth, Furqat (answer: "Ulug'imsan, Vatanim")

Method "let's grow sprouts":

It is possible to strengthen a new topic through this method. In this case, at the beginning of the lesson, students are given 1 piece of white paper. Students strengthen their knowledge on a new topic based on this method. Students draw sprouts on white paper and grow the sprouts in care. Pupils care for germination with the knowledge gained on a new topic. With each information received, one branch appears in the Sprout. In this way, germination becomes a tree and it is convenient for the teacher to determine to what extent students have mastered a new topic. In this, the interest of students in the science of Fine Arts increases, developing their thinking through the extent to which they depict the tree. To what extent readers remember the information about the life and work of the poet or Adib, along with which his creative, menaceutical abilities are formed. Students ' affection for Nature grows.

"Mosaic" method:

This is a whole-forming method of collecting pieces. To use this method, words must be written on advance cards, i.e. handouts. Students must correctly place a sequence of words and complete a given assignment. In Literature lessons, poetry, works, genre names, types of Fine Arts can be given. In addition, if images of a work are scraped and broken up, the reader can collect it and provide information about the work based on the painting. Both in the individual form of hospital education and in the group form, this method can be used effectively.

In place of the conclusion, it is worth mentioning that in the use of didactic games, which are recommended for use in Literature lessons of hospital education, there is no strict limit, which can be used in accordance with all classes. Didactic games are a great incentive for the development of students ' passion for learning. It has a particularly effective effect on students forgetting their own disease states and increasing their aspirations for life, expanding their

worldview, being able to see the good side of every reality that has happened through life events in fiction, and making the right conclusions.

References:

- 1.O'zbekiston Respublikasi Vazirlar Mahkamasining 05.05.2022-yildagi 234-son qarori
- 2.Sh.Mirziyoyev O'zbekiston prezidenti Shavkat Mirziyoyev Oliy Majlis palatalarining qo'shma majlisida so'zlagan nutqi.
- 3.D.Tursunova Gospital ta'limning boshlang'ich sinf darslarida didaktik o'yinlardan foydalanish 2023
- 4.A.Safarov, Q.Bahromov Noan'anaviy darslar va ta'limning interfaol usullari. Buxoro. 2004
5. <https://lex.uz/docs/5992724>

